

Digital twin of the Calm Water Tank Facility at the Institute of Marine Engineering of the Italian National Research Council

Mohammad Rafiei and Francesco Salvatore

Marine Propulsion and Renewable Energy Lab
CNR-INM - Institute of Marine Engineering
Italian National Research Council
Via di Vallerano, 139 - 00128 Rome (Italy)

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Authors:	Mohammad Rafiei, Francesco Salvatore
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Abstract:	<p>This report describes the realization of a comprehensive digital model of the Calm Water Towing (CWT) tank facility at the Institute of Marine Engineering (CNR-INM). The digital model describes the full infrastructure, including the tank and the towing carriage, and provides a digital twin that allows to simulate the various phases in preparation, execution and decommissioning of experimental activities in the facility. The digital twin has been developed in a Solid Works software environment and consists in a digital project, with drawings, previews, rendering and animations that can be downloaded in the most popular formats.</p> <p>In the report, the methodology has been described and examples of applications of the digital tool to ongoing and future activities are described. The activity has been undertaken and partially funded in the framework of the CNR Project ULYSSES 2030 (Underpinning Laboratory for Sea Energy Systems) and of the EU-funded project, H2020 CRIMSON, dealing with the demonstration of innovative hydrokinetic turbines for the exploitation of tidal and river energy. Nonetheless, the validity of the digital twin is general, with application to all types of testing programs in the facility.</p>

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1 Introduction

In the ever-evolving world of marine engineering, the ability to create accurate and efficient predictive models is critical. These models provide invaluable insights into the behavior of structures under various conditions, enabling engineers to take informed design decisions and accelerate the validation of new technologies. One of the most exciting developments in this realm is the concept of *digital twin*, a digital replica of a physical system that allows to simulate, predict, and optimize the performance of that system under a myriad of scenarios. The complexity of the physical system is partly described by mathematical models, with a large impact of AI (Artificial Intelligence) to dynamically refine the model with a learning process during system operation.

The digital twin technology is rapidly spreading in many industrial as well as research sectors, and the present discussion deals with an application in marine engineering. Specifically, this report describes the creation of a digital replica of the Calm Water Towing (CWT) tank facility at the Institute of Marine Engineering of the Italian National Research Council (CNR-INM). This research infrastructure falls within the class of indoor hydrodynamics testing laboratories. Small-scale models of marine vehicles and other offshore structures are towed by a motorized carriage along the tank length to simulate the relative motion between the model and the water at rest in real conditions at sea.

Calm water and wave towing tanks are crucial infrastructures for the study and development of maritime technologies. They provide a controlled environment for performing a variety of tests, such as ship resistance, propulsion, and seakeeping tests, as well as station keeping tests for offshore structures, to name a few. Creating a digital twin of such complex and vital facilities requires a meticulous approach and a thoughtful blend of traditional measurement methods and modern digital technologies.

In the digital-twin perspective, the tank, the towing carriage and the testing device are considered as an integrated physical system, and a digital, dynamic model is developed to reproduce the system and simulate its operation. It also provides a digital framework to perform multi-disciplinary analysis on system dynamics and response, as Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) studies and structural analysis studies.

The present project offers an example of how digital technology can enhance the capabilities of traditional marine testing facilities. By high-fidelity simulations of all tank testing phases, from device set-up and installation, to operation in the tank and final decommissioning, the digital model provides an innovative *design of experiment* tool.

The advantages deriving by a digital-twin support to tank testing activities are particularly apparent when the research infrastructure is used to host an *unconventional* testing campaign. This is the case, for instance, when test models are large, heavy, generating high loads and perturbations to the tank

structures. The experience of hydrodynamics testing facility managers is that such unconventional conditions are becoming more and more frequent, for both research and consultancy activities. In many cases, challenging activities are related to testing marine renewable energy systems. In fact, the most part of existing hydrodynamics testing facilities were designed decades ago for surface and underwater vehicles. These facilities now are used to host activities dealing with a variety of systems to harvest the energy of waves, marine currents, offshore winds. This trend is witnessed by new Specialist Committees recently introduced by the International Towing Tank Conference (ITTC), in response to the growing need to create a solid ground for experimental research and support to technology development in the new areas. In this framework, testing requirements for marine renewable energy systems are documented in dedicated Recommended Guidelines [1].

The digital-twin modelling activity described in this document has been undertaken in reply to a specific necessity in the framework of the H2020 CRIMSON research project [2] (2021-2024). Main objective of the project is to develop an innovative cross-flow tidal turbine and to demonstrate it at full scale in the CWT facility at CNR-INM. The 5 meter wide device of the CRIMSON project is the largest in size and output power tested ever in a towing tank infrastructure. An extremely careful design of experiment is deemed necessary to adequately face the challenges in such testing activity, and the realization of a facility digital-twin has been considered a pre-condition. Nevertheless, the impact of the present towing tank digital modelling task goes beyond a specific project, and is aimed to support facility managers daily work whenever a non-conventional testing program is scheduled.

This document describes the methodology used to develop the digital twin of the Calm Water Towing tank testing infrastructure at CNR-INM, the procedure adopted for the acquisition, verification, elaboration of data and the digitalization. The resulting digital model is presented and examples of applications to real case studies are discussed.

2 The "Pugliese" calm water towing tank infrastructure

2.1 Infrastructure data

The "Pugliese" Calm Water Towing (CWT) tank facility is one among the experimental research infrastructures available at the Institute of Marine Engineering, in Rome, Italy. This is a world class facility, one of the largest globally, 470 m long, 13.5 m wide and 6.5 m deep. The tank is equipped with a towing carriage with four Ward Leonard electrical motors generating 450 kW power to tow models up to 10 m/s. Towing speed can be controlled with 0.1% precision, and variable speed time histories during a run can be programmed. Considering its wide cross section, flow confinement effects are negligible for standard testing programs. Ship models up to 10 m length and submarine models up to 8 m length can be tested with no need to calculate blockage correction factors for measured data. Main geometry data are summarized in Fig. 1.

The facility is documented in the research infrastructure repository by ITTC [3], and is operational since 50 years. In addition to routine tests for a variety of commercial and navy ship models and

Figure 1: The "Pugliese" calm water towing tank sketch [1].

submarine models, examples of unconventional testing over the last years include airplane and hydroplane models, olympic games manned canoes, waterbykes. Recently, at the South end of the tank, an airborne ditching facility has been realized. An extension of approximately 40 meters is reserved for this installation.

Since 2011, the facility has been included in the research infrastructure portfolio of the EU-FP7 MaRINET project [4]. Thanks to the participation to this project (2011-2015) and its sequel, the H2020 MaRINET-2 project [5] (2017, 2021), the facility is rapidly become a top destination for research and technology development in the marine renewable energy sector. For its characteristics, the facility is an appealing test site for large-scale tidal energy devices.

2.2 Available documentation

At the H2020 CRIMSON project start, a recognition of existing documentation about the drawings of the facility and the towing carriage was made. The result was the identification of two references:

- hand-made sketches and executive drawings of the tank building, with construction details, hard-paper format, and

- 2D drawings of main parts of the towing carriage, digital format (DWG files).

After a careful review, the conclusion was that this documentation is not adequate for the following reasons:

- 2D drawings are difficult to be interpreted, as the structure is described only through 2D sections parallel to coordinate planes at given positions
- 2D drawings are static, that is they do not give the possibility to animate the objects and create dynamic simulation with objects in relative motion
- In the past years, the carriage has been modified, and the current layout is different from the original drawings, such as some parts have been added or removed.

The above conclusions motivate the decision to proceed with a new representation of the facility by using state-of-art technologies. However, tank drawings and the towing carriage 2D model were taken as a reference for the initial definition of geometry and dimensions. Figures 2 shows close-ups taken from the executive drawings of the tank, with details of the North side of the facility, where model set-up and deployment happens. Examples of two among the dozens of executive drawings delivered for the construction of the facility are given in Appendix A.

Figure 2: Example of hand-made executive drawings of the tank building.

The towing carriage description was available through 2D drawings realized by using the AUTOCAD software. Figure 3 illustrates the level of details from this source. These drawings were used to support the design of ad-hoc structures for specific installations. Figures 4 shows a close up of 2D drawings realized in AUTOCAD representing the support structure for installation of the TTT2 model turbine on the towing carriage. The TTT2 device was a 4-bladed, horizontal-axis tidal turbine with a 1.5 m diameter rotor. The TTT2 testing activity was performed in 2014 in the framework of the

EU-FP7 MaRINET project, as a collaboration with the Queen's University of Belfast, U.K. [7]. This was the first large-scale marine renewable energy device tested in the tank, and up to 3 years ago, it hold the record as the largest model tidal turbine ever tested in an indoor facility. Right Fig. 4 shows a phase of the turbine installation activity. Based on the 2D drawings, the actual installation of the turbine resulted into a complex and time-consuming work, as many small-but-fundamental details had not adequately foreseen in the realization of the support structure. Moreover, the installation procedure was decided step-by-step during the operations. A number of unforeseen difficulties were overcome only thanks to the excellent skills and experience of the technical staff in charge of the installation, and of the facility manager.

Figure 3: Details from the 2D drawings of the towing carriage in DWG format.

Figure 5: The mounting flanges of the carriage (left) and the 3D-model scanned by LiDAR technology (right).

to handle complex geometries and its robust simulation capabilities. Furthermore, the software's versatility to integrate with Finite Element Analysis (FEA) software such as Ansys and Comsol was another significant advantage.

3.1 The tank and the set-up area

The shape and dimensions of all details of the tank building were initially derived from the executive drawings, available as PDF scans of the hand-made originals. Where possible, dimensions were cross-checked using on-site measurements from a Laser meter. It was observed that in most cases, the information from the executive drawings was confirmed with satisfactory precision. Figure 6-top shows the basin model, while figure 6-bottom displays the water model.

For the most part of its length, the tank section has constant width and depth, 13.5×6.5 m. The two terminals, the North-side and the South-side ends present a more complex shape. In particular, the North-side end is dedicated to the set-up and deployment of test models. Particular care has been devoted to the exact survey of shape and dimensions of this part of the tank. The limited and variable width of the wetted area, and the variable depth with shallow water areas require a detailed characterization, in order to avoid that the model device may impact tank side walls or bottom during the set-up operations with the model towed back and forth by the carriage.

The 3D model includes details of the set-up area around the tank walls that can be relevant to simulate model device handling outside of the tank, by using an overhead crane.

Figure 6: The 3D model of the tank: details (top) of the set-up area (North-side terminal), and volume occupied by water inside the tank (bottom).

3.2 The towing carriage

The carriage is a massive reticular structure, composed of six modules that are bolted together using connecting flanges (figure 7). These include two symmetrical side modules, two symmetrical bottom and front modules, and two central structures. The central structures serve dual purposes: providing structural reinforcement and supporting the equipment. To create the complete carriage model, each module was created individually and then assembled together.

In addition, a structure has been added to the north side of the carriage to accommodate a crane. This crane is essential for installing the models on the carriage. Figure 8 shows a render of this added structure and the carriage's crane.

Figure 9 and figure 10 illustrate the front, top, left, and tri-axial views, respectively, of the 3D sketch and the assembled model of the entire carriage.

The modules are truss structures made from pipes, cut to size and joined using a welding process. The creation of each module utilized a functionality command available in SolidWorks called Weldment

Figure 7: View of two modules connected using flanges and bolts.

Figure 8: Support structure for the crane on the carriage.

(figure 11-top), enabling the design of a truss structure component as a single multibody part. Initially, a sketch of each module was created as a framework. Both conventional 2D sketching with different planes and 3D sketching options were used. After drawing the sketch, the Structural Member option was used to create the profiles (figure 11-bottom).

Figure 9: Front, top, left, and tri-axial views of the carriage 3D sketch.

Figure 10: Front, top, left, and tri-axial views of the carriage assembly.

Figure 11: SolidWorks features used in the creation of modules: Weldment and Structural Member.

4 The digital model

The procedure described in the previous sections was used to realize the proposed fully-3D, dynamic digital model of the parts of the testing infrastructure that are relevant during set-up, operation and decommissioning of towing tests of model devices.

The digital model is realized in a SolidWorks framework. The simulation of model device handling in the facility can be obtained by importing a CAD description of the model device into the SolidWorks project. The resulting digital model is dynamic, as relative motions among elements in the model can be simulated.

Figure 12: The CWT tank 3D rendering.

Figure 13: The carriage 3D rendering.

5 Examples of application

As mentioned in the introduction, the realization of a 3D, dynamic digital model of the tank and of the carriage has been undertaken to support a wide range of testing activities. This section describes examples of ongoing and future applications of the digital model to prepare tank testing activities for three different tidal energy devices:

- a full-scale cross-flow turbine designed by the American/Irish company ORPC,
- a cluster of 4 vertical-axis turbines, 1:9 scaled version of a 2.5 MW full scale device by the French company Hydroquest,
- a fence of 4 horizontal-axis turbines, inspired to the floating tidal turbine technology PLAT-I developed by the english company Sustainable Marine, with Schottel Hydro turbines.

All these configurations are characterized by off-standard dimensions of the models, and strong static and dynamic loads generated during operation and transmitted to the structures of the carriage.

5.1 The RivGen cross-flow turbine by ORPC and the CRIMSON project

The cross-flow turbine layout is a convenient solution to realize a device with large energy capturing elements (the blades) that can be installed also in shallow water sites. This solution allows the exploitation of powerful tidal sites where the bathymetry would not permit the effective deployment of horizontal-axis or vertical-axis turbines. Moreover, the cross-flow layout is particularly suited for installation in rivers, see Fig. 14. The ORPC company has developed the RivGen technology to the commercial stage, with examples of installations for remote communities in North America.

Figure 14: The ORPC RivGen concept [8]. Installation in a river in Alaska (left) and the 5-m wide module designed for the CRIMSON project (right).

The continuous improvement of the RivGen technology is underway in a series of research projects, including the H2020 CRIMSON Project. A 5-m wide module, with a rotor diameter of 1.8 m will be tested at the Calm Water Towing tank at CNR-INM. The activity is scheduled for Q2 2023, but the

preparatory phase was started by end 2021. Based on turbine performance estimations provided by ORPC, static and dynamic loads generated by the device during towing tests have been predicted and the design of the structures to connect the turbine with the carriage is underway. In particular, a multi-frame structure has been considered, with a module connected to the carriage, a module supporting the turbine and a structural model to interface the other two. The digital twin was then used to analyse alternative options and verify installation requirements and possible issues. Figures 15 and 16 show renderings of one option for the multi-frame configuration.

Figure 15: The H2020 CRIMSON project. Simulation of newbuild frames for turbine installation.

Figure 16: The H2020 CRIMSON project. Details of turbine coupling with the towing carriage structures.

The utilization of the digital model has informed the decision making process for the realization of the newbuild structures specifically dedicated to the RivGen turbine installation in the CRIMSON project. Specifically, a documentation has been prepared to illustrate the solution agreed by project partners CNR and ORPC to companies participating to a public bid for the manufacturing of the structures. Examples of 2D drawings exported from the digital model project under SolidWorks are given in Fig.17.

Figure 17: The H2020 CRIMSON project. 2D drawings exported from the digital model project under SolidWorks.

5.2 The HydroQuest cluster of vertical-axis turbines

The French company HydroQuest boasts a vast experience in the development of vertical-axis concepts for tidal energy exploitation. The second generation OceanQuest turbine presents a layout consisting in a cluster of 2+2 units. It has been designed for the challenging objective to realize in few years an array of 7 clusters with a total rated power of 17.5 MW in one of the most powerful tidal sites in the world, Normandy's Raz Blanchard (FloWatt project [9]). Figure 18 shows a rendering of the array with the 2+2 units clusters.

The 17.5 MW array in Raz Blanchard will be the result of a staged design and validation process, with scaled models tested in a laboratory environment and larger prototypes deployed at sea in relevant operation conditions. The Calm Water Towing tank at CNR-INM has hosted HydroQuest in 2021, in the framework of the H2020 MaRINET-2 project, to validate new design blades for a single vertical-axis model turbine. During 2022, agreements for a new testing program addressing a 1:9 scaled replica of the 2+2 units cluster of the FloWatt project have been discussed. The current schedule is to have tests completed by Q1 2023. Figure 19 shows the digital modelling of solutions to install the model cluster below the towing carriage. The digital model of tank and carriage are combined with the 3D model of the device provided by the HydroQuest company.

Figure 18: The second generation OceanQuest turbine by HydroQuest [9].

Figure 19: The HydroQuest turbine - verification of the turbine-carriage coupling solution.

5.3 Horizontal-axis turbine fence

The installation of tidal turbines by floating platforms is proposed by leading developers as an effective solution to reduce the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCoE) and make tidal energy competitive in the short term. Dealing with floating installations, the trend is to have multiple units supported by the same barge.

A remarkable example is the PLAT-I technology developed by the Scottish company Sustainable Marine Energy, with fences of 4 to 6 100-KW scale Schottel Hydro turbines for a single barge, see Fig. 20. The development of similar devices requires a careful analysis of the interference among rotors operating in proximity. The digital-twin model can be used to perform a design of experiment for such a complex layout.

Figure 20: The PLAT-I floating tidal technology by Sustainable Marine Energy designed for demonstration tests in Nova Scotia, Canada [10]

A sample application is illustrated in Fig. 21, where 4 model rotors with 0.9 m diameter are arranged in a co-planar fence and deployed in the tank. The digital model allows to simulate the phases of the installation procedures for the four devices, and, for instance, to foresee issues related to power output and measuring equipment cabling. Exporting the assembly layout to a FEA software, the correct dimensioning of supporting structures can be also done, and unnecessary structure oversizing can be avoided.

Figure 21: A horizontal-axis turbine fence: simulation of installation set-up (top) and a snapshot taken from the animation of assembly deployment into the variable-depth area of the towing tank.

6 Perspectives and conclusions

The realization of a comprehensive digital model of the Calm Water Towing (CWT) tank facility at INM has been undertaken with the objective to introduce an innovative approach to the design of experimental activities in the laboratory. The digital model, here referred to as the CWT facility digital twin, allows to simulate the various phases in preparation, execution and decommissioning of experimental activities.

The digital twin has been developed in a Solid Works software environment and consists in a digital project, with drawings, previews, rendering and animations that can be downloaded in the most popular formats.

In the report, the methodology has been described and examples of applications of the digital tool to ongoing and future activities are described.

The process of creating the digital twin is a process of continuous refinement, with each stage of the design and implementation providing additional data to further enhance the model. The ultimate aim is to provide a detailed and accurate digital representation of the tank and the carriage that closely mirrors its behavior under a variety of conditions. The realization of the digital twin of the Calm Water Towing (CWT) tank facility has been undertaken in the framework of an ongoing EU-funded project, H2020 CRIMSON, dealing with the demonstration of innovative hydrokinetic turbines for the exploitation of tidal and river energy. Nonetheless, the validity of the digital twin is general, with application to all types of testing programs in the facility.

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Figure 23: Executive drawings of Calm Water Tank building: example of side view.

